

SYNERGY AMONG HOSPITALITY EDUCATION & INDUSTRY
Mrs.Vaishali Rajarshi
Abstract:

Hospitality Industry is the most diverse and versatile industry in the world. 7 million of employment opportunities as per a review of UN world Tourism Organisation and contributes an enormous measure of income to any nation's economy. The positions offered by this industry are in assortment of areas, like inn keeping, retail, the travel industry, hospitals, agribusiness and so forth. With quick urbanization and development in the travel industry, there is a developing demand for talented skilled hospitality professionals at various departments and levels. Since 1954, when the first hospitality course started in India by Institute of Hotel management, Mumbai, there are now number of hospitality colleges in the country offering degree, diploma, and certificate courses. But there always is a considerable gap between what educators teach in the classrooms and actual knowledge required at work. With hospitality industry growing even post covid situation, there is a dire need of skilled professionals and the gap between industry and the scholarly world is expanding. The paper conceptually analyses the reasons behind the increasing gap and tries to find the solutions to bridge it. Alongside assessments of specialists from the scholarly world and industry, understudy's feelings were additionally thought of. The outcomes, according to the students were, inadequate industrial training, language barrier, lack of computer skills etc. While the experts from the business needed freshers to be more outfitted with delicate abilities like EI, time management, interpersonal relations, and they added the need of most recent practices to be included. The academicians also agree the need of an updated curriculum, but they expect more organized industrial training, increased involvement from industry to train the faculties, proper job-based skill requirements listed down which can help in defining & designing every certification level for a particular job title.

Key words: Hospitality education, hospitality skills, hospitality graduates, industrial training. Hotel industry.

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/erj/>

Introduction:

The travel Industry is the expected supporter of a nation's income, financial development, and foreign exchange earnings. WTTC's financial effect 2019 report says that Indian the travel industry Gross domestic product has expanded by 4.9% in 2019 which is third most noteworthy after Philippines and China. It adds that 6.36 million positions are made in Indian the travel industry during 2014-2019 which is 8% of the complete work of the country. Reviewing the need for skilled human resource in the hospitality/tourism industry, a tremendous growth is seen in hospitality education. Both in number of institutions and in number of students. There are more than 180 institutes in India offering different programs in tourism & hospitality. Seizing these career opportunities by providing manpower with employable skills is a challenge for the educators.

The business calls attention to the desperate need of talented work power in spite of the quantity of hospitality graduates. In an Industry academia meet at Grand Hyatt, Mumbai (2009) raised an issue of reforms in hospitality education. Accommodation experts anticipates that the students should be set up in operational abilities and in administrative capabilities like emotional intelligence, interpersonal skills, critical thinking etc. Nonetheless,

hospitality training not really give most recent industry patterns. Henceforth the understudies are not sufficiently prepared for the business necessities. So, the gap between the scholarly world and industry is truly expanding.

Academicians agree that there exists a gap between formal education & industries. Educators look upon the industry leaders for guidance in designing the programs for the competencies required for the professional success. Hospitality education being skilled based student needs to interact with the industry to sharpen their practical edge. Educators emphasizes the need of well-designed Internship program from the industry. Institute expects the students to learn latest trends of the trade during the internship as the industry is changing at a fast pace.

Long working hours, lack of work life balance and low pay cheques during industrial training discourages students to continue in this demanding industry. Absence of appropriate coaching, direction and ill-advised disposition makes the student dislike for the Industry. Multilingual abilities is a significant worry for understudies.

The above conversations can be summarised as the expanding gap between the scholarly world and industry should be spanned by cooperative endeavours in beneath referenced fields. Upgraded refreshed educational plan with dynamic association of industry experts, language hindrance, successful direction and tutoring to the understudies, research projects and supplemental classes for the educators, very much planned internships, expected ranges of skill sets for each work position are not many focuses which can help overcome any issues.

Literature Review.

Tanmoy Roy (Jan 2020): There was a robust job growth at the start of 2019. Overall, the year 2019 witnessed a significant talent shortage within the hospitality sector throughout India. Following are some statements from experts of academia & Industry.

“In India, the shortage of skilled manpower poses a serious threat to the general development of tourism. In particular, the rapid expansion of hotels of a world standard in India is creating a high level of demand for skilled and trained human resources, which can ensure the delivery of efficient, high-quality service. High standards of service are particularly important in sustaining long-term growth.” – P. Srinivas Subbarao, Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad

“I realized that there is no standard curriculum for hospitality professionals across the country. This is a highly skill-based job and requires quick thinking on your feet, improvisation and in fact an in-depth knowledge of basic skill sets. I also realized that adult training sessions fail thanks to an easy attention deficit from people. They have usually rushed sessions where tons of inputs are crammed into a little amount of your time. The engagement of the person is always on the surface level and thus the take-away is also very minor.” – Jayant Singh, Managing Partner, Tree House Hotels

Pralay Ganguli (April- Sept 2019): Has realised the important role of internship in hospitality education and writes: An internship is a phase of work experience offered by an organisation for a stipulated period. In present academic system, a student earns academic credit through internship, considered as a major tool for increasing academic grade rather than just experiential learning. He further states that: There are different research views on internship programmes in terms of the benefits from the perspectives of three main stakeholders; students, institutes and internship providing organisation. For some authors internship is just a basic course requirement for students to complete their graduation, and an opportunity to gather knowledge and experience (Seymore & Matthew, 1997; Aggett & busby 2011). This internship is also a platform for networking and interacting with the students at other institutes and the same could be beneficial for future study and job search for the students. For students, internship may be a supervised work experience where qualified supervisors guide the scholars during the training. Parent institutes offering internship

also benefited from industry by rapport building, which help in next engagement, industry support and final placement of scholars . Many researchers have identified problems with internships regarding negative attitude of interns, difficulties in accepting new challenges due to poor supervision, lack of placement opportunities, long working hours, poor working environment and interpersonal relationship, low remuneration and benefits, excessive workload, demotivate the interns and affect their career advancement. Studies have suggested that the employers are taking undue advantages from the interns where they are engaging the interns for their cost saving purpose and sometime using interns as casual labours for his or her benefits rather to coach the interns for his or her career benefits. Number of studies expressed that the internship experience may lead the dropout of interns/ students from hospitality industry, as their expectations are not met properly (West & Jameson, 1990; Barron & Maxwell, 1993; Callan, 1997; Waryszak, 1999; Zopiatis, 2007; Richardson, 2008).

Alok Kumar (2018) Kumar says: The state of hospitality education in our country is such that the institutes kept on growing unchecked. Thus, best talents are not attracted to take up hospitality as career and in turn industry has to compromise with a mediocre one. Business ethics has become a well-liked topic in both the tutorial arena and therefore the business setting within the hospitality industry. Hence, World's 2nd largest and the fastest growing industry in India is getting mediocre or substandard manpower and that too are trained by unqualified faculties and nurtured in standard less, infrastructure less, and even get equipped with an unapproved degree. There is drastic need to change the picture of hospitality education in India. Hospitality education in India has become significant in present scenario and cannot be neglected any more. There is lot of scope in higher education and research in hospitality. Though IHM's started by Central Govt.as institutes of National importance for Hospitality education in lines of IIT's and IIM's. Other Regulating bodies like AICTE and Universities have also existed but instead of setting up benchmark, they have created only more confusion in hospitality education. So, there is a need of single regulating body/university dedicated for all level of hospitality education in the country.

Kavita KM & Priyanka Sharma: After a in depth study, they concluded that freshers at entry level were not ready to work in a team. Where teamwork is the essence of hospitality. They were also found ill groomed by all departments & low on communication skills. There was a significant difference in the basic skill sets posed by the students specially food production & housekeeping departments. The industry did not expect entry level graduates to be well trained in the use of front office equipment, nor possessing the required marketing skills. They expected the candidate to find out them once they're on the work . But the freshers had no willingness to learn, were not punctual, had no good knowledge of foreign language and had a very casual approach towards safety practices. The researchers felt that it is the responsibility of educational institutions to impart basic skills more hands-on practice needed for the students in the hospitality industry. A hardworking graduate with good managerial & leadership skills will be more successful in professional life and so the educational institutions must focus on developing these skills among the students.

Bukhari & Najjar (2017) adds to different angel to the subjects expected to be learned by hospitality graduates. They state, it is an irony that a hospitality graduate is expected to learn operational skills in four main areas, conceptual skills in general and strategic management, organizational behaviour, human resource management, accounting management skills within three years which puts him under lot of pressure and mostly a graduate finishes up becoming jack of all traits and master of none. Faculty development programmes are perceived as redundant exercise by hospitality training stalwarts, the faculty members spent most of the time reading the books and imparting bookish knowledge to the students, the shortage of infrastructure and practical exposure also plays its role in making a candidate unemployable.

The student spends time imagining things, he learns from books. There is absolutely no effort made to make assignment scientific and learning exercises. They have become a mockery and two-day show.

During the interview with Hospitality Biz India (January 2011): Here the responsibility to bridge the gap lies with the industry as well as the institute. Sudhir Andrews agrees and of the opinion, that though the curriculums lag behind, it is not that easy to change it. "By the time it is brought up to date after several bureaucratic rounds, it is already outdated." Any institution cannot change the curriculum overnight since it is a comprehensive process. To bridge the gap between employment and education within the country, it's required that the tutorial institutes keep step with the changing technology and innovations. What is being taught in the institutes is completely different from what is being faced by the students at workplace. Mr. KV.Simon, states "If I have a choice, I will begin with changing the industry and not curriculum. Industry has to be educated and learn to change its own perceptions and practices and has to be built on a foundation of principles and professionalism. Industry has got to learn to respect research, education, training, compensate and offer a top quality of labor life which is attractive to its manpower . Today the industry is sitting on a judgment throne which it doesn't deserve. Once we affect the industry, we will then begin to affect the institutions/academia". According to Mr. David Naidu Director HR, Westin Gardenia, Mumbai there is a need to revisit the curriculum and review its relevance to the industry. Obsolete information and systems should be discontinued and training which is imperative to the industry today must be incorporated. Regular conducting of seminars, interaction with industry experts, workshops for personal development of faculty, etc helps in improving the overall student quality and must be undertaken by the institute. The examination and conversation reasons that overcoming any barrier between industry and the scholarly community is significant and fundamental.

Conclusion

As India is considered as one of the favourite tourist destination and also popular venue for MICE, skilled human resource is always needed in hospitality. This industry contributes to 8% of the total vacancies available in India. In developing country like us, university degree is believed to be ticket to a good job. However, it is also believed that the knowledge learnt in the classroom does not always makes a fresh graduate employable. Hospitality is majorly accepted as multidimensional Industry which provides millions of jobs for skilled and semiskilled workers and increased number of hospitality schools with ever increasing number of students, are not able to find right human resource.

As mentioned, there is always some gap in academia & industry, which can be bridged with the help of internships, apprenticeship. In spite of mandatory internship for hospitality under graduates, there is a growing concern about bridging this gap and to match the demand supply ratio.

In the wake of primary and auxiliary information, through understanding articles, research papers, blogs and talking with academicians, industry experts and understudies the end is, every stake holder should effectively meet up to redo and reengineer the hospitality schooling framework. As per the scholarly world and professionals, refreshing the educational plan is must. The business is developing quick, and institutes need to stay up with the evolving innovation. Dynamic contribution and backing from the Industry are needed for personnel advancement programs for the faculty which should be done by every teacher. Quality affirmation, innovative work cells shiould exist as well as ought to be active in all Institutes. Assignments should be innovatively planned, so the classroom information can be applied to get viable solutions. Expanded industry cooperation, genuine contextual investigations and group based instructional exercises will help develop soft skills like communication, basic reasoning, critical thinking, in the understudies.

Changing frameworks overnight will be unimaginable as execution is a long and complex cycle. Getting the latest equipment and software is a costly undertaking. In such case administration specialists like AICTE or UGC acquires the consistency in frameworks and certificates, quality checks become obligatory and normalizes the infrastructural necessities or personnel qualifications of teaching faculty, will make the understudy employable.

Industry ought to likewise do its part, for preparing right candidates. Internship is the point at which the understudy comprehends the image behind the glamorous façade of the business. Here they need to be controlled, instructed, and guided. The business should deal with them like learners and not as modest work. Long working hours, difficult work, low payments debilitate the students to proceed with their profession in Hospitality.

Students need to have a right attitude for industrial training. This can be developed during the classroom training. The determination interaction at the section level of school and for occupation can help in deciding about the correct disposition of the competitor. In view of this perceptions and ends following advances are suggested for overcoming barrier between the scholarly community and Industry.

Recommendations:

1. Uniformity in framework in terms of teaching hours, infrastructure requirements and duration of course should be done on national level.
2. Upgradation of syllabus in view with industry requirements and execution with industry involvement to understand the fast-evolving technology.
3. Faculty developments program with on-the-job training and knowledge refreshment capsule.
4. Assignments with genuine contextual investigations which supports basic reasoning and inventiveness of the understudies. Supplant the obsolete old points and showing procedure with most recent innovation and new, creative, and intelligent strategies.
5. Students should be made aware of importance of safety practices, good grooming, punctuality, and subjects like sustainability.
6. Industry ought to have a very much organized internship program where understudies get familiar with the new most recent practices and make a positive network for future profession. They ought to be guided for the branches of their interest and ought to be regarded for their interests.
7. Likewise, industry must genuinely list down the required ranges of abilities for each work position. This will help the instructors in planning the syllabus and characterize the degree of information for each qualifying capability, like diploma level will be for semi-talented competitors or degree for section level and so on. This will likewise help in get specialization of departments at graduation level.
8. The big brands like Oberoi hotels have a skill development centre of its own OCLD, like wise if hospitality institution can be affiliated or associated with hotels. This will help in getting on the job training to the students as they work while they are studying and will also help develop managerial skills.
9. Industry demands the managerial skills from the fresh graduates but, these skills can be expected from master's program. At university level students already get overwhelmed with many subjects as operational, non-operational, soft skills etc.

References

- Kumar A (2018) Hospitality Education in India: Issues and Challenges. *J Hotel Bus Manage* 7: 169. doi: 10.4172/2169-0286.1000169

ERJ

Educreator Research Journal

Volume–VIII, Issues– IV

July - Aug 2021

- Asirifi, G. H., Doku, V., Morrison, S. & Sackey, A. S. (2013). The Gap between the Hospitality Education and Hospitality Industry. *Journal of Education and Practice*. Vol.4, No.24, 2013 19. Retrieved from: <http://www.iiste.org>.
- Pralay Ganguli (2019) Internship Practices in the Hospitality Sector in India: A Career Benefit or Precarious Experience. *Journal: Mahatma Gandhi Central University Journal of Social Sciences MGCUISS Volume-I, Issue 1, April-September 2019*
- Ashaq Hussain Najar¹, Syed Aasif M. Bukhari², Assistant Professor (Central University of Kashmir), INDIA, Gap Analysis in Hospitality Education, and Industrial Requirements. Volume-7, Issue-4, July-August 2017 *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research* Page Number: 170-173
- Gaurav Bathla¹ & Dr. Jashandeep Singh² & Dr. Amrik Singh Chauhan³. HOTEL INDUSTRY EXPECTATIONS VERSUS ACADEMIC DELIVERABLES, GAP ANALYSIS WITH REFERENCE TO PUNJAB STATE. *IJRAR- International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews [VOLUME 5 I ISSUE 4 I OCT. – DEC. 2018]*
- KAVITA KM AND PRIYANKA SHARMA, Gap Analysis of Skills Provided in Hotel Management Education with Respect to Skills Required in the Hospitality Industry: The Indian Scenario. *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Systems* Volume 4 Issue 1, 2011 ISSN: 0947-6250 Print
- <http://www.hospitalitybizindia.com/detailNews.aspx?aid=10017&sid=5> Cover story, Bridging the gap Monday, January 17, 2011, 15:45 Hrs [IST]
- <https://www.stoodnt.com/blog/hospitality> Evolution of the Hospitality Sector, Career Scopes and Growing Demand for Trained Hospitality Professionals in India Posted on January 2, 2020 By Tanmoy Ray